

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL ISSUES OF THE FORMATION OF THE CULTURE OF SPEECH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING

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Annotation: This article briefly discusses the main signs of the concept of “pedagogical conditions”, the definition of a set of pedagogical conditions in the formation of skills in the culture of speech in Primary School students, the analysis of the nature of the pedagogical possibilities of communication, the integrative approach to establishing the educational process in a new content and new form, the technological

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A condition is a condition that determines one or another consequence, and when the occurrence of that end interferes with one process or phenomenon, it has a positive effect on another. The important thing is that the condition is considered in relation to the existence, validity and development of one thing or another-an object, phenomenon, event and state. In turn, the condition to be imposed will have its own meaning in relation to something-an object, phenomenon, process, system, etc. Thus, in the philosophical level analysis of a volitional problem, the need to clarify the conditions is an important methodological requirement for any study of something-an object, phenomenon, process and systems. Since any activity in pedagogy is considered in terms of the development of personal qualities, all of them together ensure the effective development of the individual, we can and should talk about the pedagogical conditions of the effectiveness of the implementation of these types of activities. Proceeding from the philosophical definition, we can consider the conditions for the effective development of an individual as a set of circumstances in which it is realized and which make it possible for this process to be successful. In this case, the following are included in the cases: a) objects of reality in the world; b) subjects of the process of carrying out various types of activities; C) peculiarities of the process of formation and development of an active personality; g) means, methods and forms of organization and implementation of this process.

The main signs of the concept of "pedagogical conditions" are as follows:

- a set of external objects of the educational environment in which the subject of research is in a certain relationship;
- a set of internal characteristics (States, qualities) of the subject of research, on which the solution of the problem depends to one degree or another;
- a set of external objects and internal characteristics determines the presence, validity and development of the subject of research (effective solution of the tasks set).

If we sum up the identified signs, the following definition of the concept of” pedagogical conditions ” is formed: pedagogy is put in front of it and is a set of forms, content, methods and objective possibilities of material and spatial environments aimed at solving the problems that arise consciously in the educational process, the implementation of which ensures a more

effective course of these processes. Based on this, researchers can distinguish and consider a set of external and internal conditions. It is unlikely that this concept will be clarified for each separately taken case. When determining the set of pedagogical conditions, it is necessary to take into account the main components of the subject, the composition of the environment surrounding it, the characteristics of the subject's relationship with the environment, the types of activities carried out. Without these conditions, it is impossible to find a solution to the problem, but they are not enough to solve it with maximum efficiency.

Determining the set of pedagogical conditions in the formation of skills in the culture of speech in primary school students, we were guided by the requirements for the education of the native language imposed by modern society, the content of language education for Primary School students.

Pedagogical views on communication, its essence, significance and role in the educational process made it possible to note:

- a) communication in the history of domestic and foreign pedagogy, the appeal to communication is associated with a person's need for self-realization, development of consciousness and manifestation of independence (J. Dyui, I.G. Pestalossi, L.N. Talstay, K.D. Ushinsky and others);
- b) Communication is a situation of searching for the essence of values and strengthening them in experiences and actions (E.V. Bondarevskaya, Z.I. Vasilyeva, I.A. Kolesnikova, A.P. Tryapisina and others);
- c) communication-anthropocentrism, provides understanding and sadness, manifests individuality in a person (R.Yu.Khudoyberganov, V.Diltey, E.I.Kazakova, A.G.Rivin and others);
- g) education with culture and within culture, on the one hand, ensures that a person enters social life and communication in his natural way, and on the other hand, it is through communication that the assimilation of cultures takes place (T.G. Braje, I.S. Gracheva, A.V. Wise and others).

At the moment, an analysis of the nature of the pedagogical possibilities of communication has made it possible to reveal its humanistic nature: the existing connections between communication – conversational – conversation – discussion – discussion – discussion – discussion – discussion-open discussion, which are recorded directly in the relationship of people, can be transferred from discussion to dialogue through discussion, joint efforts and cooperation; the discussion can be; communication makes it possible to openly state its goals, not to violate cultural traditions, to facilitate the transfer of accumulated cultural heritage from generation to generation, to support and develop the dialogue of time and culture.

An integrative approach is required when establishing the educational process in a new content and new form. The word integration comes from the Latin word “integratio” – restoration filling, “integer” – from the whole word. Integration is a process of convergence and connection of disciplines carried out in conjunction with differentiation processes, which helped to create new, whole, holistic departments, and carried out interdisciplinary Communications, was highly visible [118; 211]. It allows you to set a new content of the reader's activity. Integration as an educational goal is not to give knowledge indicating the connection of individual parts of the universe, but to teach the child to imagine a holistic universe in which all its elements are interconnected.

In this place, the individual appears as a subject with the possibility of cooperation. It manifests itself as a subject that harmoniously interacts with nature, with the socio-cultural

environment, as well as with the past and the future, such as: knowledge-based-Gnostic, creative-creative, sensory-exciting, rational-analytical, activity-communication. Without oneself, a person cannot manifest himself only as a subject of external communication. That is why only when he understands himself will he be able to realize others. Requirements of the principle of cooperation: 1) education is carried out not as a process of unilateral authentication of norms and values, but as a mutually harmonious activity of the teacher and the Student; 2) education and upbringing is the mutual harmonious development of students, acquaintance with each other, knowledge in cooperation; the main subject is the students themselves, their harmonious relationships and

Based on the principle of Organization of own activities: the reader must be able to transform himself. It is important that the educational and educational process is aimed at the development of the qualities of self-analysis, self-discipline and independent activity in students.

When solving typical problematic tasks in the educational process, it is important to take into account the cognitive reserves of students, to provide for the expansion of the scale of their mental activity.

In problem educational situations, the student independently assimilates the information from the inside, choosing and harmonizing the important ones. As a result, new knowledge, skills and abilities are formed in students, they put forward their hypotheses, feel the need for independent research.

The technological task of an integrative approach in education is manifested in:

- save time;
- harmonization of educational information and creation of an opportunity for students to master them intensively;
- to ensure the continuity and continuity of this process in order to expand the scope of knowledge and skills of students;
- presence of mutual diversity;
- harmonization of subjects and academic subjects in one category;
- ensuring and systematizing the consistency of knowledge, skills and abilities mastered by students;
- exchange of some knowledge acquired by students with new information in this direction;
- content of integrated qualities in students, ensuring their coordination and mutual consistency.

The central place among the tasks of integrative rejuvenation is occupied by the task of developing the educational activities of students.

The organization of classes on the basis of an integrative approach makes it necessary to abandon outdated methods. As a result of such integration, a qualitative change occurs in the learning process.

As positive results of the integrative approach in the educational process, the following are distinguished:

1. Students are provided with a deep and solid assimilation of the relatively completed part of the material under study.
2. Favorable conditions are created to attract students to various forms and forms of activity, to optimally integrate the gross, group and individual forms of Organization of activities together.

3. Wide opportunities are created for the joint creativity of the teacher and students.

4. The teacher will have the opportunity to integrate into the forms that ensure the activity of students in the course of the lesson.

5. Conditions arise to take into account the age, mental, physical characteristics and interests of the pupil.

The analysis of literature on the issue under discussion makes it possible to note that the skill of oral and written expression of one's thoughts was not considered the goal of education in the primary class in the second half of the 20th century, since society did not feel the need for it. Both reading and writing are speech skills and skills and rely on knowledge of the language system (phonetics, graphics, lexicon, grammar, orthography), the ability to build one's own speech and understand other people's speech. Children who have mastered written speech are able to understand the features inherent in the text – a story, description, discussion, the content of a Popular Science article, etc., get acquainted with their stylistic differences. Written speech and oral speech were considered only as a form of speech associated with the expression and perception of thoughts, and were considered a tool for learning to read and speak. However, there are differences and similarities between them.

First of all, we will focus on the description of written speech with oral speech. The oral and written manifestations of speech are “connected to each other by thousands of transitions.” This can be explained by the fact that on the basis of both oral speech and written speech, internal speech lies, it is with its help that thought is formed.

Thought-derived from the Arabic word *quot*; thought, idea; means the meaning of reason, thought, thought, Fantasy, reflection. In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, thought is defined as an illusion, an illusion about something, a phenomenon or someone.

In addition, oral speech can be written on paper or using technical means. Despite the commonality of oral and written speech, there are also differences between them. The differences between oral and written speeches are as follows:

- oral speech-sounding, pronounced speech. It is considered the primary form of the existence of language, the form opposite to written speech. In the conditions of innovative education, oral speech in terms of the possibilities of its distribution in reality is not only overtaking written speech, but also gaining such an important advantage as the speed of information transmission;

- written speech is speech described on paper (parchment, birch bark, stone, cloth, etc.) using graphic symbols designed to designate speech sounds. Written speech is considered secondary, contrasted with oral speech, and is considered a later form of language existence according to the time of its appearance.

A number of psychological-situational character differences are also distinguished between oral and written speech:

1. In oral speech, the speaker and the listener see each other, which makes it possible to change the content of the conversation depending on the reaction of the interlocutor. There is no such possibility in written speech: a person writing can fantasize only a probable reader;

2.

Differences, similarities of oral and written speech

3. Oral speech is intended to be perceived by hearing, and written speech – by sight. The expression of oral speech through letters is usually carried out using special technical means, when in written speech the reader has the opportunity to re-read the written text any time. In the same way, the person who is writing also has the opportunity to repeatedly improve the written text;

4. Written speech brings communication to a clear, recorded state. It connects the communication of people of the past, present and future, manifests itself as the basis of communication and scientific activity on work, while oral speech is often distinguished by its ambiguity, non-completeness, delivery of a common opinion.

Thus, in oral and written speech, along with a series of similarities, there are also differences that distinguish one from the other. When identifying similarities in them is based on the fact that the literary language is considered the basis for both the flour of speech and for this, the means of their expression give rise to specific differences.

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